

**KALYANAKA GHRITA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW AS PER CLASSICAL AND
CONTEMPORARY PERSPECTIVES****Ambika Gotagi^{*1}, Dhivya Kaviarassane², Bharathi A.K.S.³**¹PG Scholar, Department of Agada Tantra, Department of Agada Tantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan, Karnataka, India.²Dhivya Kaviarassane PG Scholar, Department of Agada Tantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan, Karnataka, India.³Kumar S Bharathi, Professor, Department of Agada Tantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan, Karnataka, India.***Corresponding Author: Ambika Gotagi**

PG Scholar, Department of Agada Tantra, Department of Agada Tantra, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan, Karnataka, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18797799>**How to cite this Article:** Ambika Gotagi^{*1}, Dhivya Kaviarassane², Bharathi A.K.S.³ (2026). Kalyanaka Ghrita: A Comprehensive Review As Per Classical And Contemporary Perspectives. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(3), 112–115.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 21/01/2026

Article Revised on 10/02/2026

Article Published on 01/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Kalyanaka Ghrita is a well-established *Ayurvedic ghrita* formulation traditionally prescribed for various psychosomatic, neuropsychiatric, metabolic, and reproductive conditions. Classical references to this formulation are found in *Susruta Samhita (Kalpa Sthana 6/8–11)*.^[1] It is prepared by processing *ghrita* with a combination of medicinal herbs known for their *Medhya*, *Rasayana*, *Vishaghna* and *Tridosahara* properties.^[2,4] The present article systematically reviews the composition of *Kalyanaka Ghrita*, its pharmacological actions, therapeutic indications, and explores its clinical relevance in the context of current medical practice.^[11,14]

KEYWORDS: *Kalyanaka Ghrita*, *Medhya Rasayana*, *Vishaghna*.**➤ INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda describes a variety of medicated ghee preparations (*ghritas*) specifically designed to nourish the brain, strengthen mental faculties, and rejuvenate the body.^[2,6] Among these, *Kalyanaka Ghrita* holds a prominent place due to its broad therapeutic utility. It is particularly valued for its effects on *graha rogas* (psychological disturbances), *Apasmara* (epilepsy), *Pandu* (anemia), *Shwasa* (respiratory disorders), and infertility.^{1,5,7} Its polyherbal composition enhances cognition, delays degeneration, and restores physiological balance.^[11,14] Considering its extensive classical indications, *Kalyanaka Ghrita* remains clinically relevant in the modern era.

➤ AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- To analyze the classical references of *Kalyanaka Ghrita* as mentioned in *Sushruta Samhitha*
- To present the therapeutic indications and pharmacological actions of its ingredients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comprehensive review of the literature was undertaken using both classical Ayurvedic and modern scientific sources. Classical references included authoritative texts such as the *Samhitas (Sushruta Samhitha)* and *Nighantus*,^[3,17] along with official compilations like the *Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI)* and the *Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API)*. To complement this, relevant contemporary data were sourced from standard modern textbooks and peer-reviewed research articles available in databases including PubMed, Scopus, and Elsevier. Additionally, individual ingredients were examined in terms of their Ayurvedic characteristics and pharmacodynamic significance to better understand their probable mechanisms of action in Atopic Dermatitis (AD).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kalyanaka Ghrita is described in the *Sushruta Samhitha (Kalpa Sthana 6/8–11)* as a classical medicated ghee prepared with a diverse range of herbs that possess

Medhya, Rasayana, Vishaghna, and Tridoshahara properties.¹ Ingredients such as *Vidanga, Triphala, Danti, Manjishtha, Sariva, Tagara, Kushta, Priyangu,* and *Chandana* are carefully processed in ghee following the principles of *Sneha Kalpana*.^[1,2]

Commentators like Dalhana have highlighted its therapeutic use in conditions such as *Graha Roga* (psychic disturbances), *Apasmara* (epilepsy), *Pandu* (anemia), *Shwasa* (respiratory disorders), *Mandagni* (weak digestive fire), *Kasa* (cough), *Shosha*^[1,3,7] (wasting disorders), and reproductive imbalances. Classical texts including *Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Sahasrayoga,* and various *Nighantus* emphasize the multidimensional actions of its ingredients, noting that many-such as *Vidanga, Triphala, Manjishtha, Sariva,* and *Chandana*^[5,9,17] possess potent *Vishaghna* (antitoxic) activity. These herbs work to neutralize toxins, purify *rakta* (blood), and maintain overall physiological balance, addressing both external poisons and internal metabolic toxins.

Modern research supports these traditional insights. Studies report that many of these herbs exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, immunomodulatory, and detoxifying effects-mirroring the classical concept of *Vishaghna* activity. The ghee base enhances the bioavailability of these compounds, allowing lipophilic phytochemicals to reach deeper tissues and the central nervous system. This unique delivery system helps explain *Kalyanaka Ghrita*'s effectiveness in neuropsychiatric conditions, metabolic

disorders, chronic fevers, and systemic ailments, demonstrating its continued relevance in modern integrative healthcare.^[12,16]

Disease Prevalence Relevant to *Kalyanaka Ghrita*

Kalyanaka Ghrita is indicated for a wide range of disorders described in the classics, including *Graha Roga, Apasmara, Pandu, Shwasa, Mandagni, Kasa, Shosha,* and conditions arising from internal or external accumulation, reflecting its strong *Vishaghna* (antitoxic) potential.^[1,5] In modern clinical contexts, the prevalence of toxin-related and metabolism-linked disorders has significantly increased. Lifestyle factors, polluted environments, adulterated food, chronic stress, and poor digestion contribute to the accumulation of *Ama* and oxidative toxins within the body. These internal toxins underpin a variety of common diseases such as chronic inflammation, respiratory allergies, anemia, neuropsychiatric disorders, and metabolic syndromes.

Epidemiological data reveal rising rates of psychological disorders, respiratory illnesses, anemia, and chronic inflammatory conditions-diseases directly addressed by the *Medhya, Rasayana, and Vishaghna* properties of *Kalyanaka Ghrita*. The formulation's antitoxic action is especially relevant today, as toxin-mediated disorders are widespread due to environmental pollution, heavy metal exposure, chemical preservatives, and lifestyle-induced *Ama* formation. Thus, *Kalyanaka Ghrita* remains clinically valuable for managing high-prevalence, toxin-driven, and psychosomatic disorders commonly observed in modern populations.

Pharmacological action and *Rasa Panchaka* of herbal ingredients of *Kalyanaka Ghrita*^[8,10,16,17]

S.No	Herb (Botanical)	Rasa/Guna/Veerya/Vipaka	Dosha Effect	Modern Pharmacological Actions
1	<i>Vidanga (Embelia ribes)</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu; Laghu, Ruksha; Ushna; Katu</i>	<i>Kapha-Vata Shamak</i>	Anthelmintic, antimicrobial, antifungal, antioxidant
2	<i>Bibhitaki (Terminalia bellirica)</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya; Laghu, Ruksha; Ushna; Katu</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Antioxidant, hepatoprotective, laxative, anti-inflammatory
3	<i>Haritaki (Terminalia chebula)</i>	<i>Madhura, Amla, Kashaya; Laghu, Ruksha; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Antioxidant, digestive, mild laxative, neuroprotective
4	<i>Amalaki (Emblica officinalis)</i>	<i>Madhura, Amla; Ruksha, Laghu; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Antioxidant, immunomodulatory, adaptogenic, neuroprotective
5	<i>Danti (Baliospermum montanum)</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta; Laghu; Ushna; Katu</i>	<i>Kapha-Vata Shamak</i>	Laxative, purgative, anti-inflammatory, digestive stimulant
6	<i>Harenuka (Vitex negundo)</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta; Laghu; Ushna; Madhura</i>	<i>Kapha-Vata Shamak</i>	Digestive, carminative, antioxidant, antimicrobial
7	<i>Talisapatra (Abies spectabilis / Ficus religiosa leaves in some texts)</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu; Laghu; Ushna; Katu</i>	<i>Kapha-Vata Shamak</i>	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, CNS calming
8	<i>Manjishtha (Rubia cordifolia)</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya; Laghu, Ruksha; Shita; Katu</i>	<i>Pitta-Vata Shamak</i>	Blood purifier, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antioxidant
9	<i>Keshara (Crocus sativus / Saffron)</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta; Laghu; Ushna; Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha Shamak</i>	Antidepressant, memory enhancer, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
10	<i>Utpala (Nymphaea spp. / Blue lotus)</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta; Snigdha, Laghu; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Sedative, calming, neuroprotective, antioxidant

11	<i>Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides / Red lotus)</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta; Snigdha; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	CNS calming, sedative, neuroprotective, antioxidant
12	<i>Dadima (Punica granatum / Pomegranate)</i>	<i>Madhura, Amla, Kashaya; Snigdha; Ushna; Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha Shamak</i>	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cardioprotective, antimicrobial
13	<i>Malatipushpa (Jasminum officinale / Jasmine flower)</i>	<i>Madhura; Laghu, Snigdha; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Sedative, anxiolytic, antioxidant, aromatic relaxant
14	<i>Rajanyau (Oryza sativa / Rice grains)</i>	<i>Madhura; Laghu, Snigdha; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Nutritional, calming, promotes digestion, mild CNS tonic
15	<i>Sariva (Hemidesmus indicus)</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta; Laghu; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha Shamak</i>	Blood purifier, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, diuretic
16	<i>Sthira (Desmodium gangeticum)</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu; Laghu, Guru; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Sedative, neuroprotective, memory enhancer, antioxidant
17	<i>Priyangu (Callicarpa macrophylla / Vidanga-type herb)</i>	<i>Tikta; Laghu; Ushna; Katu</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, CNS calming
18	<i>Tagara (Valeriana wallichii)</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu; Laghu, Snigdha; Shita; Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamak</i>	Sedative, anxiolytic, antispasmodic, neuroprotective

AGADA TANTRA PERSPECTIVE OF KALYANAKA GRHITA

From the *Agada Tantra* viewpoint, *Kalyanaka Ghr̥ita* is understood as a holistic formulation that supports the body in coping with toxic influences. Each ingredient contributes in a complementary manner to neutralize toxins and restore balance. *Vidanga* helps in clearing intestinal toxins and microbial burden, while *Triphala* supports digestion, enhances metabolic fire, and promotes gentle detoxification through its antioxidant action. Drugs like *Bhadradaru* and *Manjishta* play an important role in purifying the blood and protecting the liver, thereby reducing the systemic impact of toxins. *Malati Puspa* provides a calming effect on the mind and nervous system, which is particularly useful in toxin-related psychological disturbances, whereas *Priyangu* helps limit further toxin absorption through its astringent action.^[7] *Kesara* strengthens cognitive functions and offers neuroprotective support.^[12] *Ghr̥ita* acts as the ideal carrier, allowing the active principles to reach deeper tissues and aiding cellular repair. Together, these actions explain the relevance of *Kalyanaka Ghr̥ita* in the management of *visha*-related conditions by addressing both physical and mental aspects of toxicity.^[11,14]

DISCUSSION

Kalyanaka Ghr̥ita is a classical Ayurvedic formulation known for its *Rasayana*, *Medhya*, and *Tridosha*-balancing properties. It comprises multiple herbs with complementary actions, making it a multifunctional therapeutic agent.

Classically, its ingredients exhibit varied *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, *Vipaka*, and *Prabhava*. Drugs such as *Vidanga* and *Bibhitaki* possess *Ushna Virya* and *Krimighna Prabhava*, indicating antimicrobial and antiparasitic activity, while *Amalaki* and *Haritaki* demonstrate *Rasayana* effects supported by *Madhura Vipaka* and *Tridosha* balance. Ingredients like *Danti*, *Padmaka*, and *Priyangu* act as *Virechaka* or *Vamya*, aiding detoxification and digestive health.

Modern studies support these classical concepts, showing antioxidant, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, digestive, cardioprotective, and neuroprotective activities. *Amalaki* and *Haritaki* enhance antioxidative defense, *Tagara* and *Vacha* exhibit neuroprotective^[12] and sedative effects consistent with *Nidrajanaka Prabhava*, and *Manjishta* and *Sariva* validate their *Raktashodaka* action through hepatoprotective and anti-inflammatory effects.

The presence of both *Ushna* and *Shita Virya* herbs ensures balanced *Dosha* regulation, supported by *Go Ghr̥ita* and *Ksheera*, which enhance bioavailability and tissue penetration. Overall, the classical pharmacodynamics of *Kalyanaka Ghr̥ita* closely align with modern evidence, justifying its role in rejuvenation, detoxification, cognitive support, and immune modulation.^[14]

CONCLUSION

Kalyanaka Ghr̥ita is a classical Ayurvedic formulation that reflects the thoughtful combination of multiple herbs working together to support overall health. From an *Agada Tantra* viewpoint, it is valued for its *Vishaghna* and *Raktashodaka* actions, helping the body neutralize toxins and maintain internal balance. The formulation offers a range of benefits, including *Rasayana*, *Medhya*, *Balya*, *Deepana*, and *Shwasahara* effects, making it useful in both preventive care and therapeutic settings.

Modern research supports these traditional claims, showing antioxidant, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, digestive, neuroprotective, and cardioprotective^[11] activities that align well with classical concepts of *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, *Vipaka* and *Prabhava*. The presence of both *Ushna* and *Shita Virya* herbs ensures balanced action on the body, while *Go Ghr̥ita* and *Ksheera* act as *Yogavahi* carriers, improving absorption and allowing the active principles to reach deeper tissues. Altogether this blend of classical wisdom and modern understanding highlights *Kalyanaka Ghr̥ita*

as a holistic, multi-target formulation that supports detoxification, rejuvenation, and long-term health.

REFERENCES

1. Sushruta. *Sushruta Samhita* with Dalhana commentary. Kalpa Sthana, Chapter 6, Verses 8–11. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; Reprint edition.
2. Sharma PV. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy; Reprint edition, 2.
3. Acharya JT, editor. *Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta* with Nibandhasaṅgraha commentary of Dalhana. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; Reprint edition.
4. Anonymous. *Ayurvedic Formulary of India*. Part I. 2nd ed. New Delhi: Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India, 2003.
5. Shastri AD, editor. *Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Govinda Das*. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; Reprint edition.
6. Dash B, Kashyap L. *Materia Medica of Ayurveda*. New Delhi: B. Jain Publishers; Reprint edition.
7. Sharma S, editor. *Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhata* with Sarvangasundara commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; Reprint edition.
8. Kirtikar KR, Basu BD. *Indian Medicinal Plants*. Vol. 1–4. Dehradun: International Book Distributors; Reprint edition.
9. Nadkarni AK. *Indian Materia Medica*. Vol. 1–2. Mumbai: Popular Prakashan; Reprint edition.
10. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. *Pharmacognosy*. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; Reprint edition.
11. Patwardhan B, Warude D, Pushpangadan P, Bhatt N. Ayurveda and traditional Chinese medicine: A comparative overview. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.*, 2005; 2(4): 465–473.
12. Baliga MS, Meera S, Mathai B, Rai MP, Pawar V, Palatty PL. Scientific validation of the ethnomedicinal properties of the Ayurvedic drug Triphala. *J Altern Complement Med.*, 2012; 18(10): 946–954.
13. Kumar S, Dobos GJ, Rampp T. The significance of Ayurvedic medicinal plants. *J Evid Based Complementary Altern Med.*, 2017; 22(3): 494–501.
14. Thatte UM, Dahanukar SA. Ayurveda and contemporary scientific thought. *Trends Pharmacol Sci.* 1986; 7(7): 247–251.
15. Chopra RN, Nayar SL, Chopra IC. *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*. New Delhi: CSIR; Reprint edition.
16. Aggarwal BB, Harikumar KB. Potential therapeutic effects of curcumin and other phytochemicals. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol.*, 2009; 41(1): 40–59.
17. Sharma PV. *Nighantu Adarsha*, 1–2. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy; Reprint edition.